

Cellular Fluxes

- 1 Cell lysis
- 2 Degradation
 - a) biodegradation
 - b) photodegradation
 - c) depuration

Food Web Fluxes

- 3 Consumption (inhalation or ingestion)
- 4 Excretion
- 5 Osmotic uptake

Transport Fluxes

- 6 Sedimentation
- 7 Resuspension/ Diffusion
- 8 Aerosolization
- 9 Hydrologic Import/Export